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To cite this article: Stefan Boes & Yanmei Liu (24 Dec 2023): Do individuals with better health insurance system knowledge make better decisions about their health plans?, Applied Economics, DOI: [10.1080/00036846.2023.2295303](https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2023.2295303)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2023.2295303>

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Published online: 24 Dec 2023.

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Do individuals with better health insurance system knowledge make better decisions about their health plans?

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ABSTRACT

Choice-based health insurance systems require individuals to be proficient in selecting a suitable health plan. However, individuals are not always well informed, possibly leading to suboptimal decisions. We use representative survey data from Switzerland to study the association between individuals' objective knowledge about the health insurance system and one dimension of health plan choice, namely voluntary deductibles. Our results suggest that individuals with better health insurance system-related knowledge are more likely to opt for a high-deductible plan when being in good health and are more likely to opt for a low-deductible plan when having higher health care needs, which is in line with the financial incentives set by these plans. We discuss our results by exploring different sources of information gaps, potential adverse health effects, and moral hazard.

KEYWORDS

Choice-based health insurance; health insurance system knowledge; health insurance literacy; insurance deductibles; moral hazard

JEL CLASSIFICATION

I13; D81; D91; C25

I. Introduction

Health insurance literacy (HIL) plays a major role in making decisions about health insurance. HIL is defined as the 'degree to which individuals have the knowledge, ability, and confidence to find and evaluate information about health plans, select the best plan for their own (or their family's) financial and health circumstances, and use the plan once enrolled' (Quincy 2012, 7). Individuals who lack a sufficient level of HIL may find it difficult to select a suitable health plan, especially in the presence of multiple interrelated choice options, e.g. levels of cost-sharing and coverage or access restrictions. Suboptimal health plan choices do not only lead to unnecessary spending on health insurance but also affect care-seeking behaviour and negatively impact individuals' health (e.g. Adepoju, Mask, and McLeod 2018; Kim, Braun, and Williams 2013; Paez et al. 2014).

Previous research has demonstrated that consumers often have a limited level of HIL (e.g. Barcellos et al. 2014; Bartholomae et al. 2016; Brown 2018; Loewenstein et al. 2013; McCormack et al. 2009; OECD 2008; Paez and Mallery 2014). This may explain why some individuals are

overwhelmed by the complexity and variety of health plans on offer (Bhargava, Loewenstein, and Sydnor 2017; Ericson and Sydnor 2017) or unable to calculate out-of-pocket costs (Paez and Mallery 2014; Parragh and Okrent 2015). Different measures of HIL have been proposed in the literature covering various dimensions of knowledge and skills (e.g. Bardy 2023; Bardy and Boes 2022; Paez et al. 2014). We focus here on context-specific knowledge about the Swiss health insurance system, which constitutes this study's setting, and we use the term health insurance system knowledge (HISK) to emphasize the differentiation to more generic measures of HIL.

We aim to test empirically whether individuals with higher levels of HISK are more likely to choose a high-deductible plan when they are in good health compared to individuals with lower levels of HISK, and vice versa, whether they are more likely to choose a low-deductible plan in case of higher health care needs. The underlying hypothesis is that HISK is a decisive factor in navigating the health insurance system, operationalized here as the cost-minimizing deductible choice for a given health status. For the latter, we explore

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a feature of Switzerland's mandatory health insurance system, namely the financial incentives set by voluntary insurance deductibles. While the minimum deductible of CHF 300 per year is associated with the highest monthly premiums, higher deductible levels of CHF 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, or 2500 allow for cost savings on premiums. However, vis-à-vis expected health care expenditures, the system favours the lowest deductible in the case of high expected health care costs, whereas the highest deductible would be the recommended choice in the case of low expected health care costs in order to minimize overall spending; see Figure 1. We hypothesize that individuals with higher levels of HISK, due to awareness of this mechanism, are more likely to follow the financial incentive, while individuals with lower levels of HISK deviate from it.

This hypothesis directly builds on the literature investigating the association between consumer knowledge and health insurance decisions (e.g. Bes et al. 2017; Colón-Morales, Giang, and Alvarado 2021; Hoerl et al. 2017; Loewenstein

et al. 2013; Sainfort and Booske 1996; Scanlon, Chernew, and Lave 1997). Following this literature, we do not assume that deductible choice is deterministic, but rather allow for a probabilistic relationship with HISK. This is important because there may be other factors that influence decision-making. Some of them are observed in our data, such as socio-economic background, while others are unobserved or measured insufficiently, like the respondents' specific health care needs, risk and time preferences, and non-health expenditures.

Using representative survey data on HISK, insurance deductibles, subjective health, and socio-economic background of individuals, we apply ordered logistic regressions to investigate the relationship between HISK and the choice of low-, medium- and high-deductible health plans. Our results indicate that levels of HISK are positively associated with levels of insurance deductibles, and to a greater extent if the individual is healthy. While the former association is mainly a result of selection, i.e. individuals with better HISK tend to choose higher-deductible health plans because of

Figure 1. Out-of-pocket spending as a function of health expenditures by type of health plan. The graph shows the relationship between out-of-pocket spending on health care and insurance premiums as a function of health expenditures depending on the level of the health insurance deductible (different levels are marked on a greyscale as indicated in the figure legend). The Swiss health insurance system requires individuals to cover their incurred health expenditures up to the chosen deductible level per year (except for a few services and treatments that are excluded, e.g. costs related to maternity). Beyond the deductible, individuals must cover 10% of the additionally incurred health expenditures up to a stop-loss of CHF 700 per year. Health insurance premiums are set at the averages in 2021 per deductible level across all insurers and premium regions in Switzerland in the basic health plan (free choice of provider), extracted from www.priminfo.ch.

their background characteristics, the latter interaction of HISK with health status confirms our hypothesis and remains stable across model specifications. We find evidence for significant knowledge gaps, especially regarding coinsurance rates and the use of deductibles, which is indicative of a limited awareness of how health plans translate into out-of-pocket spending. These gaps are particularly prevalent in individuals with lower socioeconomic status or migration background. However, we do not find evidence that HISK would be associated with the utilization of health care services, suggesting that suboptimal insurance decisions associated with lower HISK do not necessarily translate into moral hazard beyond the already existing incentives set by the health insurance system.

Our paper contributes to the literature in at least three, albeit related dimensions: First, there is a growing interest in how choice quality in the context of health insurance can be characterized and what factors facilitate or hinder good-quality decisions (e.g. Handel et al. 2023; Winter and Wuppermann 2019). Our innovation here is to link a regulatory aspect of Switzerland's choice-based mandatory health insurance system with a novel measure of HISK to understand whether and to what extent knowledge about the insurance system is associated with insurance choice quality. Second, HIL and HISK are still relatively new concepts, and previous literature has mainly focused on the US (e.g. Paez and Mallery 2014; Adepoju et al., 2018; Edward et al. 2019; Vardell 2019). Recent studies have highlighted the need to expand research on HIL and HISK to other countries with choice-based insurance systems, such as the Netherlands and Switzerland (Bardy 2023; Holst et al. 2022), and our study takes a novel step to investigate HISK as a determinant of insurance choice quality. Third, even though our study is mainly descriptive and does not allow for causal inferences on the effect of HISK on insurance decision-making, our analysis shows a significant association of HISK with the quality of insurance choices and identifies important inequalities in the distribution of HISK in the Swiss population. The latter heterogeneity is of concern to policymakers given the Federal Council's health policy strategy to 'empower citizens to make well-

informed, responsible and risk-aware decisions that determine their own health' (FOPH 2019). Knowledge gaps call for action to improve literacy in the Swiss population on aspects related to health insurance, and possibly design interventions that help individuals make better decisions.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section II outlines the main features of the Swiss health insurance system that are relevant to our study. Section III describes the data and methods. Section IV presents the results, and section V discusses them in light of previous evidence. The final section critically reflects on the analysis and concludes the paper.

II. Institutional background

Residents in Switzerland are obliged to have basic health insurance. The basic health insurance market follows the principles of managed competition (Schmid, Beck, and Kauer 2018). Available health plans differ in terms of the insurance provider, the level of deductibles, and self-imposed restrictions on the access to health care providers in managed care plans. Consumers can contract with any insurance provider and switch providers every year (open enrolment). Deductibles apply to both basic and managed care plans, and for individuals aged 19 and over, they are standardized at a basic annual deductible of CHF 300, as well as five voluntary higher deductibles ranging from CHF 500 to CHF 2500 per year. Once the yearly deductible level is reached, consumers pay a 10% coinsurance up to a stop-loss of CHF 700 per year.

Community-rated premiums are regulated by the government and vary according to age group (children 0–18 years, young adults 19–25 years, and adults 26+ years), insurer, and place of residence. Individuals who choose a voluntary higher deductible benefit from premium rebates (Kreier and Zweifel 2010; Schmid, Beck, and Kauer 2018). Tax-financed premium subsidies are offered to low-income households, and approximately 30% of the population is eligible for such subsidies (Kaufmann, Schmid, and Boes 2017; Trottmann, Zweifel, and Beck 2012). For further details about the health insurance system, see, for example, de Pietro et al. (2015) and Schmid et al. (2018).

In a choice-based health insurance system, like the one in Switzerland, a sufficient level of HISK (and HIL) is a prerequisite for making informed decisions and, consequently, for an efficient functioning of the insurance market. Although deductibles and benefits are standardized in the Swiss compulsory health insurance system, plan choice is still complex due to the numerous choice options. This study focuses on the choice of deductibles. On the one hand, we do not have access to information about the individual's insurance provider, and thus cannot infer insurance premiums on an individual level, or access restrictions in managed care plans. On the other hand, knowledge about deductibles (or copayments) reflects an individual's ability to compare the costs and benefits of an insurance plan (Hoerl et al. 2017). While high-deductible plans are typically associated with lower monthly premiums, they have different implications on out-of-pocket spending. In particular, individuals with lower expected health expenditures can reduce their out-of-pocket spending by choosing a high-deductible plan, whereas for individuals with higher health care needs, a low-deductible plan is typically the cost-minimizing option. Figure 1 depicts this elementary feature of the Swiss system with 2021 reference premiums. However, not all individuals may be aware of this feature, or they may find it difficult to translate expected health expenditures into an optimal deductible level.

III. Data and methods

Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021

The data for the study are taken from the 'Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey', a nationally representative survey conducted by a market research institute in October 2021 (intervista AG), mandated by the University of Lucerne as part of a project financed by the Swiss National Science Foundation (<https://p3.snf.ch/Project-188851>). A total of 6,036 randomly selected individuals aged 26 to 75 years filled in the online questionnaire in any of the Swiss languages (German, French, or Italian). Quotas were used for age, gender, education, and geographical distribution based on the national statistics in

Switzerland. Individuals from the Italian-speaking region were oversampled to avoid small cell sizes, and we used sample weights in all our analyses. Given the design of the project, only individuals who have made a previous decision regarding health insurance, either for themselves or for others, were included in the survey. The questionnaire was comprised of 31 questions covering various topics, including the respondents' HISK, health insurance, health status, health care utilization, and socio-economic and demographic background information. The demographic and socio-economic factors included gender, age, education, place of residence, nationality, employment status, household size and income, marital status, and risk and time preferences. Due to missing information on education and other background variables, the number of observations used for the analysis was reduced to 5,577; for additional details on the survey, the validity and reliability of the included measures, and the sample properties, see Bardy (2023).

Variable definitions

Definitions of the outcome and predictor variables are presented in Table 1. HISK was assessed based on two principal questions. The first contained a sequence of six true/false statements covering various features of the Swiss health insurance system. The second asked respondents to translate a medical bill into out-of-pocket spending based on a given deductible and accounting for the coinsurance rate. While this entails some numeracy skills, we considered the understanding of common insurance terms such as deductibles and copayments as decisive for answering this question correctly and, therefore, included it as part of HISK. Based on the seven responses recorded for an individual, we constructed a simple score adding up the number of correct responses (0–7) such that individuals with higher values are considered to have higher levels of HISK. The distribution of HISK scores in the sample is shown in Figure A1 in the Appendix. Based on this distribution, we also defined a categorical HISK variable, which classifies individuals as low (HISK score 0–3), medium

Table 1. Variables and definitions.

Variable	Definition
<i>Health insurance choice</i>	
Deductible amount	Annual deductible: CHF 300, 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500
Deductible (3 categories)	Annual deductible in 3 categories: low (300, 500), medium (1000, 1500, 2000), high (2500)
<i>Health insurance system knowledge</i>	
HISK score	0–7 for the number of correct responses to the following true/false statements (1–6) and the question on out-of-pocket spending (7): (1) You can choose your coinsurance rate. (False) (2) Health insurers have the right to decline someone’s application for a supplementary health insurance contract. (True) (3) Everyone is eligible for premium subsidies. (False) (4) Cost-sharing refers to the costs that are shared between the insured person and the health insurer. (True) (5) The coinsurance is the amount that you must pay once your yearly deductible is reached. (True) (6) The premium is a specific amount charged for a specific health care product (e.g. drug) or a specific service. (False) (7) Suppose you have a yearly deductible in basic insurance of CHF 2000, and you did not have health expenditures in the current year yet. The coinsurance rate is 10% up to the maximum out-of-pocket spending of CHF 700. The medical bill you receive displays an amount of health care expenditures of CHF 2300. How much do you have to pay out-of-pocket for this CHF 2300 bill? Correct answer: CHF 2030.
HISK categories	HISK score in three categories: 0–3 (low), 4–5 (medium), 6–7 (high); midpoints of intervals are used for model-based predictions
<i>Health status</i>	
Chronic illness	1 if chronic or permanent illness in the last 6 months or current health condition will last at least for 6 months, 0 else
Subjective health status	Self-perceived health status in 3 categories: 1 for very good health, 2 for good health, 3 for fair or poor health
<i>Health care utilization</i>	
Number of doctor consultations	The number of doctor consultations in the past 12 months (all types of physicians except dentists)
<i>Demographic and socio-economic background</i>	
Age	Age in years
Female	1 for women, 0 for men
Education	Highest educational attainment in 3 categories: up to lower secondary education (low), upper secondary (medium), tertiary degree (high)
Household income	Household monthly gross income (in CHF) in 4 categories: up to 6,000, 6,001–9,000, 9,001 or higher; household income missing
Risk preference	Willingness to take risks as a score (1–5) where 1 means not willing to take any risks to 5 completely willing to take risks
Time preference	Willingness to give up something today to benefit in the future as a score (1–5) where 1 means not willing at all to 5 completely willing
Non-Swiss	1 if non-Swiss, 0 if Swiss
Region of residence	In 3 categories for the language regions: German, French, Italian

Source: Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021.

(4–5), and high (6–7) levels of HISK. The primary purpose of this grouping was to simplify the exposition of results.

Descriptive statistics

Summary statistics for all variables are provided in Table 2, divided by the three categories of HISK. On average, individuals with a lower level of HISK are more likely to choose a low-deductible than a high-deductible plan compared to individuals with a higher level of HISK. Health, measured by a chronic or long-term illness and by subjective health, is more or less equally distributed across the three HISK groups. However, individuals with higher levels of HISK are, on average, more likely to be younger and Swiss, with higher levels of educational attainment and higher income, and they are more likely willing to take risks and have

higher levels of patience. In addition, we observe significant differences by language region, with relatively more individuals from the French-speaking part in the high-HISK group and relatively more individuals from the Italian-speaking part in the low-HISK group.

The differences between individuals with lower and higher levels of HISK will be further examined below using statistical models and techniques, particularly whether HISK is associated with deductible choice depending on a person’s health status (our main objective). Moreover, we will assess how strong the different background characteristics are associated with the HISK score, and in which domains of HISK there are more knowledge gaps. Finally, we will assess whether HISK is associated with health care utilization, measured by the number of doctor consultations in the year prior to the interview, conditional on health status and insurance

Table 2. Descriptive statistics.

	Health Insurance System Knowledge			<i>p</i> -value
	Low 1204.0 (965.8)	Medium 1292.1 (999.7)	High 1408.5 (1038.4)	
Deductible amount				
High deductible	30.3%	36.1%	44.4%	<0.001
Chronic illness	38.4%	38.8%	39.2%	0.921
Subjective health status				0.048
<i>Very good</i>	21.9%	21.2%	23.3%	
<i>Good</i>	53.9%	56.7%	57.1%	
<i>Fair or poor</i>	24.2%	22.1%	19.6%	
Number of doctor consultations	4.03 (6.74)	4.21 (8.12)	4.46 (10.97)	0.471
Age	51.8 (14.1)	50.6 (13.4)	45.8 (13.3)	<0.001
Female	49.0%	51.0%	47.4%	0.083
Region of residence				<0.001
<i>German</i>	71.6%	74.6%	70.4%	
<i>French</i>	23.5%	21.8%	26.1%	
<i>Italian</i>	4.9%	3.6%	3.5%	
Non-Swiss	12.9%	7.5%	7.8%	<0.001
Education				<0.001
<i>Up to lower secondary</i>	10.3%	5.6%	2.8%	
<i>Upper secondary</i>	75.0%	74.7%	69.6%	
<i>Tertiary</i>	14.7%	19.7%	27.6%	
Household income				<0.001
<i>Up to 6,000</i>	35.8%	30.9%	27.7%	
<i>6,001–9,000</i>	25.1%	26.5%	24.2%	
<i>9,000 or higher</i>	21.0%	26.2%	33.0%	
<i>Missing</i>	18.1%	16.4%	15.1%	
Risk preferences	2.21 (1.16)	2.35 (1.09)	2.45 (1.10)	<0.001
Time preferences	3.18 (1.15)	3.35 (1.06)	3.40 (1.03)	<0.001
Number of observations	1,276	2,846	1,455	

Source: Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021, own calculations.

Reported numbers are sample proportions for the categories shown. Sample means are reported for the deductible amount, the number of doctor consultations in the past 12 months, age, risk, and time preferences (standard deviations in parentheses). For the variable definitions, see Table 1. The last column shows *p*-values for the null hypothesis of equal (means) across the three HISK groups using χ^2 -tests (*F*-tests).

deductibles, to evaluate whether HISK may be related to moral hazard. The related statistical models will be briefly described next before presenting the results.

Statistical models

The primary focus of our analysis is to investigate how HISK is associated with deductible choice.¹ Given the financial incentives set by the insurance deductibles in the Swiss system, we expect that healthier individuals, on average, are more likely to choose a higher-deductible plan, while less healthy individuals are more likely to choose a low-deductible plan. However, not all individuals may be aware of these incentives and the relationship between out-of-pocket spending and own health care expenditures (as described in Figure 1). Hence,

in combination with HISK, we hypothesize that the above expectation is stronger for individuals with higher levels of HISK, while individuals with lower levels of HISK may choose a high-deductible plan less often when healthy, or too often even when having high health care needs.

The hypothesis is tested using an ordered logistic regression model (e.g. Greene and Hensher 2010). The probability of observing a specific deductible level is given by

$$\Pr(y = j|x) = \frac{\Lambda(\kappa_j - x'\beta) - \Lambda(\kappa_{j-1} - x'\beta)}{1 - \Lambda(\kappa_{j-1} - x'\beta)}, j = 1, \dots, 6 \quad (1)$$

where y denotes deductible choice with $j = 1, \dots, 6$ representing levels CHF 300, 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, and 2500. x represents the vector of explanatory variables in the model, and β is a vector of unknown parameters to be estimated from the data along with the threshold parameters κ_j ,

¹Note that we do not aim at identifying causal effects in this study due to the observational nature of our data and the inherent endogeneity of HISK. HISK and HIL are, among other things, formed by the insurance decision-making of individuals (reverse causality or even simultaneity) and driven by confounding influences, such as individuals' abilities, skills, family and social background. Instead, we focus here on investigating the association between HISK and insurance choices, which is still informative in a descriptive sense to understand better whether individuals with higher HISK make higher-quality insurance decisions.

where κ_0 is assumed minus infinity and κ_6 infinity. The function $\Lambda(z)$ represents the cumulative density of the logistic distribution with $\exp(z)/(1+\exp(z))$. The parameter vector β shows the direction of the association between the explanatory variables and the outcome. However, for ease of interpretation, predicted probabilities and their changes will be reported below to examine the link between HISK and deductible choice.

The vector of explanatory variables x contains as main elements (a) the HISK score, (b) indicators for health status, and (c) the interaction of the HISK score with health status. We expect the interaction terms to be positive with indicators for good health, which would provide evidence in favour of our hypothesis that individuals with higher levels of HISK are more likely to choose a high-deductible plan when healthy. We estimate two different models, the first with chronic illness as the health indicator, and the second with indicators for subjective health. The reasoning is that we want to assess whether the two health indicators provide signals of different strengths such that HISK may matter more (or less) in the deductible choice (McCormack et al. 2009). The two models also provide a robustness check to see whether a specific health status measure drives the results. In each case, we first estimate the model without additional explanatory variables and then include the characteristics listed in Table 1 as controls. Since chronic illness indicates higher health care needs, and 'very good health' is chosen as the reference category for subjective health status, the expected sign of the interaction terms in our estimated models is negative (but with the same underlying hypothesis).

In supplementary analyses, we explore the determinants of the HISK score using linear regressions estimated by ordinary least squares. We also use Poisson regressions to examine the association between the HISK score and the number of doctor consultations. For more details about these models, see, for example, Cameron and Trivedi (2005). Robust standard errors are used for inference in all models, and all analyses were executed in Stata 17.

IV. Results

Figure 2 summarizes the main results of the paper. Based on the ordered logistic regressions for deductible choice, we find that individuals with better HISK are more likely to choose a high-deductible plan than individuals with lower HISK, conditional on being in good health. This result is depicted in Figure 2, panel A (left) for individuals without a chronic illness and panel B (left) for individuals with very good subjective health status. As shown in the graph, the probability of choosing a high-deductible plan is around 5–10% points higher for the high-HISK group compared to the low-HISK group, and vice versa, the probability of choosing a low-deductible plan is around 5–10% points lower, while the probability of a medium-deductible plan is about the same across the HISK groups. These results are conditional on the other explanatory variables in the model, i.e. after controlling for individuals' demographic and socio-economic background characteristics, and risk and time preferences (full estimation results are shown in Table A1 in the Appendix).

The left panels of Figure 2 also show that the probability of choosing a high-deductible plan is higher for individuals with very good subjective health than those without a chronic illness. One possible explanation for this result is that the indicator for subjective health reflects a person's overall health status, which is a broader term and captures more facets of the individual's health and health care needs. Consequently, we may interpret an excellent subjective health status as a clearer signal for low expected health expenditures, which individuals may have internalized, and therefore, they may be more likely to choose a high-deductible plan. On the other hand, even in the absence of a chronic illness, a low-deductible plan may still be the cost-minimizing option for an individual due to other health care needs.

The two graphs on the right-hand side in Figure 2 indicate that subject to poor health (presence of a chronic illness in panel A and fair or poor subjective health in panel B), the probability of choosing a low-deductible plan is around 60% for the low-HISK and 70–80% for the high-HISK group, i.e. a 10–20% point difference. Vice versa, the probability of choosing

Figure 2. Levels of HISK and deductible choice by health status. *Source:* Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021, own calculations. The four graphs show predicted probabilities of respondents reporting a low/medium/high deductible by levels of HISK and health status (see Table 1 for a definition categories). Predictions are calculated from ordered logit models for the deductible amount (CHF 300, 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, or 2500) with specifications as shown in Table A1 in the appendix (panel A is calculated from model (2), panel B from model (4) in Table A1). Probabilities are conditional on the sample means of the control variables. Panel A shows probabilities conditional on respondents having no chronic illness (left) or having a chronic illness (right). Panel B shows the probabilities conditional on respondents having very good subjective health status (left), or fair or poor subjective health status (right). The whiskers show 95% confidence intervals.

a medium- or high-deductible plan is around 10–20% points lower for the high-HISK than the low-HISK group. Thus, the differences in deductible choice conditional on poor health are even more significant across HISK groups than for individuals in good health. Again, these results are adjusted for background characteristics, i.e. differences in income, education, gender, and age, or in risk and time preferences do not drive these differences by levels of HISK. Moreover, the differences are sizable as, for example, the probability of choosing a high-deductible plan in the low-HISK group with poor subjective health is about 25%, which is almost double that in the high-HISK group.

Since individuals in poor health, on average, have significantly higher health care needs and medical expenditures, a sub-optimal deductible choice likely results in higher than necessary out-of-pocket spending, and there are potential cost savings by choosing a low-deductible plan. To assess whether the observed patterns in deductible choice indeed indicate more cost-conscious decision-making in the high-HISK group, we can use the number of doctor consultations in the past year as a proxy for health care needs in further estimations. Our data suggest that individuals with very good subjective health had approximately 1.7 doctor consultations on average, while individuals in fair or poor subjective health had approximately

9.2 doctor visits. These averages vary somewhat by HISK, with 1.6/8.2 for the low-HISK group and 1.9/9.8 for the high-HISK group. However, the implications regarding out-of-pocket spending are very much comparable. More specifically, assuming one physician visit costs around CHF 300–400 per doctor visit (rough estimate based on data provided by the Federal Statistical Office on the total yearly cost of ambulatory care, average doctor consultations per year and capita, and population numbers, see <https://www.bfs.admin.ch/bfs/de/home/statistiken/gesundheit.html>), for individuals in very good subjective health, the deductible associated with the lowest expected overall spending is CHF 2500, while for individuals in poor health it is CHF 300 (Figure 1). This result also holds when looking at the average number of doctor visits for individuals without a chronic illness (2.1) and those with chronic illnesses (7.6). Thus, it seems that individuals with higher levels of HISK indeed make a better deductible choice than those with lower levels of HISK, at least in terms of their total out-of-pocket spending.²

Table 3 quantifies the results shown in Figure 2 by calculating predicted probabilities, and changes in predicted probabilities for point increases in the HISK score, by chronic conditions and subjective health. Baseline probabilities are calculated for a HISK score of zero. Changes in predicted probabilities indicate how the probabilities of choosing a low-, medium-, or high-deductible plan on average increase or decrease, with each additional point on the HISK score, conditional on sample means of the other control variables in the model. Confirming the results shown in Figure 2, for individuals in good health, the probability of choosing a low-deductible plan decreases, whereas the probability of choosing a high-deductible plan increases with each additional point on the HISK score, and vice versa for individuals in poor health.

The regression estimates indicate that the association between HISK and deductible choice is at least partly driven by individuals' background characteristics (compare Table A1 in the Appendix). As one would expect, age (related to

the experience in making health plan choices), education (related to knowledge and literacy in general), and income (related to available resources and likely also to knowledge) are particularly important in explaining the positive association between HISK and deductible level. However, the interaction terms of health status and the HISK score in the different models remain basically unchanged even after the inclusion of the control variables, i.e. the differences reported in Table 3 and Figure 2 between the high- and low-HISK groups by health status (chronic illness or subjective health status) do not seem to be driven by these factors. In addition, we also tested other variables in the models, like having a supplementary insurance plan, employment status and job type, family structure (being married or in a registered partnership, and having kids in the household), home-ownership, political orientation, sports and leisure activities, and internet usage. None of these variables influences the association between the HISK score and deductible choice.

V. Discussion

Health insurance system knowledge and related gaps

The results of our study indicate that individuals with higher levels of HISK are more likely to select a high-deductible plan when in good health, and they are more likely to select a low-deductible plan when in poor health, controlling for a rich set of background factors. The HISK score used in our study measures the respondents' comprehension of various features of the Swiss health insurance system. A higher HISK score may partly demonstrate respondents' ability to navigate the system and weigh the costs and benefits of different health plans. Good comprehension skills may also increase their ability to process insurance-related information and facilitate the understanding of complex insurance concepts. Studies mainly from the U.S. suggest that most individuals understand that they must pay monthly premiums, but they have problems understanding cost-sharing terms such as

²We also tested for heterogeneity in this result by gender, age, region of living, educational background, income, and nationality, but none of these differences turned out significant in the regressions.

Table 3. Average marginal probability changes for HISK score by health status.

	Deductible		
	Low (CHF 300, 500)	Medium (CHF 1000, 1500, 2000)	High (CHF 2500)
<i>A. Model with chronic illness (self-stated)</i>			
Marginal probability changes for HISK score by			
a. No chronic illness	-0.0069 (0.0054)	-0.0006 (0.0005)	0.0075 (0.0060)
Baseline	0.3841	0.1874	0.4285
b. Chronic illness	0.0141** (0.0069)	-0.0044** (0.0022)	-0.0097** (0.0047)
Baseline	0.6044	0.1612	0.2344
<i>B. Model with subjective health status</i>			
Marginal probability changes for HISK score by			
a. Very good subjective health	-0.0155* (0.0086)	-0.0029* (0.0017)	0.0184* (0.0095)
Baseline	0.3731	0.1823	0.4445
b. Good subjective health	0.0036 (0.0062)	-0.0002 (0.0004)	-0.0034 (0.0057)
Baseline	0.4395	0.1825	0.3779
c. Poor or fair subjective health	0.0336*** (0.0086)	-0.0111*** (0.0029)	-0.0225*** (0.0057)
Baseline	0.5324	0.1726	0.2950

Source: Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021, own calculations.

Reported numbers are conditional marginal probability changes for the HISK score calculated from ordered logit models for the deductible amount (CHF 300, 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, or 2500) with specifications as shown in Table A1 in the appendix (panel A is calculated from model (2), panel B from model (4) in Table A1). Baseline probabilities are evaluated for a HISK score of 0 as reference point. Marginal probability changes are calculated for point increases on the HISK score by health status (chronic illness in panel A, subjective health status in panel B, categories for each indicated by small letters) and conditional on sample means of the control variables. For a description of the variables, see Table 1. Robust delta-method standard errors are reported in parentheses. Number of observations in each model: 5,577. Significance levels: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Figure 3. Proportion of respondents correctly responding to HISK questions. Source: Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021, own calculations. The graph shows the proportion of respondents correctly responding to the questions constituting the HISK score. Q1-Q6 are based on true/false statements to the following questions: Q1. You can choose your coinsurance rate. (False) Q2. Health insurers have the right to decline someone's application for a supplementary health insurance contract. (True) Q3. Everyone is eligible for premium subsidies. (False) Q4. Cost-sharing refers to the costs that are shared between the insured person and the health insurer. (True) Q5. The coinsurance is the amount you must pay once your yearly deductible is reached. (True) Q6. The premium is a specific amount charged for a specific health care product (e.g. drug) or a specific service. (False). The bottom bar is based on the following question, Q7. Suppose you have a yearly deductible in basic insurance of CHF 2000, and you did not have health expenditures in the current year yet. The coinsurance rate is 10% up to the maximum out-of-pocket spending of CHF 700. The medical bill you receive displays an amount of health care expenditures of CHF 2300. How much do you have to pay out-of-pocket for this CHF 2300 bill? Correct answer: CHF 2030. The distribution of the number of correct responses per individual (HISK score) in the sample is shown in Figure A1 in the appendix.

deductibles or coinsurance (e.g. Barcellos et al. 2014; Loewenstein et al. 2013; Norton, Hamel, and Brodie 2014; Paez et al. 2014). Our study builds on the assumption that a reasonable level of HISK is imperative for consumers to understand the key features of insurance products and reduce barriers to selecting a suitable plan.

When looking at the components of the HISK score, Figure 3 highlights that some respondents tend to show a better understanding of health insurance terms and concepts, whereas others demonstrate more limited literacy and numeracy. As displayed in Figure 3, more than 80% know that insurers have the right to decline someone's application for supplementary health insurance and that not everybody is eligible for premium subsidies in basic insurance. However, in line with previous literature (e.g. Barcellos et al. 2014; Bartholomae et al. 2016; Bhargava, Loewenstein, and Sydnor 2017; Nobles et al. 2018; Paez et al. 2014), we find that less than 65% responded correctly to questions regarding coinsurance, copayments, and premiums. Especially the distinction between deductibles and coinsurance, and how to calculate the amount of out-of-pocket spending of a given medical bill, seem to be less straightforward, with roughly half of the respondents giving an incorrect answer. Only about 25% of the respondents answered six or all seven questions correctly, while about the same proportion answered three or fewer questions correctly (see also Figure A1 in the Appendix).

These supplementary results point to the existence of key information frictions. Some consumers unfamiliar with basic health insurance terms and concepts may find it challenging to choose an adequate health plan. From an individual's perspective, if expected health care expenditures are low, then there is a monetary benefit in choosing a high-deductible plan, *ceteris paribus*, due to the premium rebates associated with these plans. Low-deductible plans, on the contrary, are more likely to benefit people with chronic health conditions or higher expected health expenditures due to the lower treatment costs that must be paid (at full price) out of pocket. One possible explanation of

the results found in this study is that individuals with higher HISK are more likely to be aware of this mechanism, and they may have higher levels of health literacy in general, i.e. they may also be better at anticipating their future health care needs. If this is the case, and individuals with higher levels of HISK are more likely to make better or better-informed health plan choices, then this calls for interventions to improve HISK and facilitate decision-making in the context of health insurance (see also Hoerl et al. 2017). This, on the other hand, requires a good understanding of the sources and determinants of information frictions, which can at least partly be revealed by our study.

Determinants of health insurance system knowledge

Table 4 summarizes the estimates of two linear regression models for the HISK score. Column (1) shows the results for a model that only takes into account demographic and socio-economic background characteristics (variables listed in Table 1), while column (2) adds health status (chronic illnesses and subjective health) to the model. The results indicate that age, being Swiss, having a higher education or income, and the presence of a chronic illness are strong predictors of the HISK score. Experience effects might explain these differences, i.e. certain groups of individuals have more experience navigating the health insurance system than others. However, there are also likely differences in cognitive and non-cognitive skills in addition to experience that can explain why, for example, individuals with higher education and higher income have, on average, higher levels of HISK. This latter hypothesis is partly confirmed by the result that risk and time preferences are positively associated with HISK scores, even after controlling for education and income, and these preference parameters have been shown to correlate with personality traits (e.g. Borghans et al. 2008; DellaVigna 2009).

However, it should be noted that the models for the HISK score, as shown in Table 4, have a relatively

Table 4. Determinants of HISK score and health care utilization.

	HISK score		Number of doctor consultations		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
HISK score			1.007 (0.0186)	1.029 (0.0169)	1.024 (0.0167)
Chronic illness		0.211*** (0.0458)		2.384*** (0.111)	2.101*** (0.0972)
Subjective health status (ref.: Very good)					
<i>Good</i>		0.0318 (0.0495)		1.403*** (0.103)	1.319*** (0.0966)
<i>Fair or poor</i>		-0.107 (0.0677)		2.658*** (0.239)	2.365*** (0.218)
Age	-0.0152*** (0.0015)	-0.0161*** (0.0015)		0.998 (0.0019)	0.995* (0.0019)
Female	0.0353 (0.0394)	0.0377 (0.0395)		1.221*** (0.0576)	1.178*** (0.0552)
Region of residence (ref.: German)					
<i>French</i>	0.0354 (0.0464)	0.0411 (0.0464)		0.948 (0.0581)	0.958 (0.0585)
<i>Italian</i>	-0.137* (0.0704)	-0.118* (0.0706)		0.912 (0.0581)	0.914 (0.0576)
Non-Swiss	-0.522*** (0.0781)	-0.526*** (0.0782)		1.167** (0.0863)	1.169** (0.0854)
Education (ref.: Lower secondary)					
<i>Upper secondary</i>	0.508*** (0.0887)	0.510*** (0.0888)		0.912 (0.0880)	0.939 (0.0889)
<i>Tertiary education</i>	0.761*** (0.0982)	0.776*** (0.0984)		0.885 (0.0918)	0.962 (0.0988)
Household income (ref.: Up to 6,000)					
6,001–9,000	0.0879* (0.0509)	0.0954* (0.0509)		0.864** (0.0554)	0.876** (0.0547)
9,001 or higher	0.255*** (0.0520)	0.257*** (0.0520)		0.867** (0.0577)	0.892* (0.0585)
Missing	-0.0367 (0.0601)	-0.0267 (0.0603)		0.936 (0.0774)	0.925 (0.0746)
Risk preferences	0.0309 (0.0192)	0.0371* (0.0194)		0.892*** (0.0240)	0.923*** (0.0246)
Time preferences	0.0542*** (0.0197)	0.0576*** (0.0196)		0.991 (0.0254)	0.997 (0.0254)
Deductible (ref.: CHF 300)					
<i>CHF 500</i>					0.736*** (0.0404)
<i>CHF 1000</i>					0.860 (0.188)
<i>CHF 1500</i>					0.780 (0.125)
<i>CHF 2000</i>					0.631*** (0.0815)
<i>CHF 2500</i>					0.537*** (0.0306)
Constant	4.444*** (0.146)	4.375*** (0.151)	4.103*** (0.335)	2.192*** (0.412)	3.244*** (0.643)
<i>F-statistic/Wald statistic</i>	30.51	26.07	0.14	1332.64	1679.45
<i>R-squared/McFadden's R-squared</i>	0.0648	0.0690	0.0000	0.2451	0.2653
<i>Akaike Information Criterion</i>	19511.5	19492.0	53241.6	40225.4	39161.9
<i>Number of observations</i>	5,577	5,577	5,577	5,577	5,577

Source: Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021, own calculations.

Columns 1 and 2 report estimated coefficients from linear regression models for the HISK score. Columns 3 to 5 report estimated coefficients in exponentiated form (incidence rate ratios) from Poisson regression models for the number of doctor consultations. As a reference point, the mean number of doctor consultations in the total sample is 4.21; the standard deviation is 8.52. Robust standard errors are reported in parentheses. Significance levels: * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

low explanatory power with an R-squared of only around 6%. Apart from possible refinements in functional form specification, the low R-squared highlights that HISK is a complex concept with

many aspects determining how much individuals know about the local health insurance system, and health insurance in general (i.e. individuals' HIL). More research is needed to better understand the

determinants of HISK and HIL and inform policy about possible ways of improving insurance decision-making with targeted interventions.

Moral hazard and potential adverse health effects

If individuals with higher levels of HISK are more likely to be aware of the incentives set by high- and low-deductible plans, then an immediate follow-up question is whether HISK is also associated with changes in health care utilization. For example, individuals with lower levels of HISK may be more likely to have a high-deductible plan even when in poor health and then forego necessary health care due to the higher treatment costs needed to be covered out of pocket. It could also be that individuals with a lower level of HISK are more likely to choose a low-deductible plan even when in good health, and given the higher coverage, they have an incentive to consume more health care than necessary. Such observations would be in line with findings in the literature, providing ample evidence that higher deductibles are associated with lower medical care consumption (e.g. Alessie et al. 2020; Gardiol, Geoffard, and Grandchamp 2005; Gerfin and Schellhorn 2006; Trottmann, Zweifel, and Beck 2012; Zweifel and Manning 2000). While at least part of this association can be attributed to self-selection into different deductible plans, there is also a moral hazard effect (e.g. Alessie et al. 2020; Leu et al. 2009). With our data, we can test whether HISK is associated with the number of doctor visits as a simple measure of health care consumption, and we can also test whether this association changes once individuals' background characteristics and insurance status are controlled for in the model.

Table 4 reports the results of the related Poisson regressions. Overall, we do not find evidence that the HISK score would be associated with the number of doctor consultations. This holds in the simple bivariate relationship, when adding health status and other background characteristics to the model, when controlling for deductibles, and it is also true when estimating the association separately for the extensive and intensive margins (going to the doctor, yes/no, and the number of doctor consultations conditional on going to the doctor). On the other hand, regarding the background variables, we find

common patterns as reported in the literature (e.g. Santos Silva and Windmeijer 2001; Boes and Gerfin 2016; Deb and Trivedi 2002): women, older adults, and those with poor health or less income, on average, have a higher number of doctor visits, while those with a higher insurance deductible have a lower number of doctor consultations; see also Kenkel (1990), Dwyer and Liu (2013), and Schmid (2015) for a link between consumer information and health care demand.

Study limitations and future research

The measure of HISK used in this study is naturally context-specific and cannot be generalized to other health insurance systems. It addresses individuals' understanding of selected key features of the Swiss health insurance market. However, for practical reasons, the survey design cannot cover all domains of the insurance system. Other features not accounted for here may also be important in the decision-making process, such as the quality of services and premiums offered by different insurers, types of health plans, local supply, and possible bundling with supplementary health insurance. While we deem our measure of HISK a good proxy for this more comprehensive understanding of the Swiss health insurance system, further research is needed to validate our findings by accounting for additional domains of HISK and, through a cross-country comparison, investigate whether there are specific features of health insurance systems that facilitate or impede individuals' insurance decision-making.

All our statistical analyses are based on survey data. This comes with the usual limitations, especially regarding coverage of specific population groups, which may not be well represented in our sample. Furthermore, the survey was fielded during the COVID-19 pandemic, which means that awareness of health insurance may be higher than usual. It would be important to repeat the study in a few years to assess the development of HISK and its association with health plan choices and to investigate whether the pandemic context has driven our results.

Moreover, due to the cross-sectional observational study design, our estimations do not account for individual unobserved heterogeneity

or dynamics of choices, and there is no exogenous variation in HISK. Consequently, it is not possible to draw causal conclusions, and therefore, we were careful in interpreting our results descriptively only. For example, for our secondary results, i.e. how HISK is associated with health care utilization, the HISK score is likely endogenous because individuals who use the health care system more often, or have more doctor visits, might be more familiar with the health insurance system. This reverse causality, along with possible unobserved confounding influences, would bias a causal regression analysis, and the reported association likely overestimates the true causal effect. Given the small and statistically insignificant association between HISK and doctor visits, even after controlling for health status and deductibles, this would imply that higher HISK scores could, in fact, lead to fewer doctor consultations in a causal research design. Whether this is indeed an effect of HISK or HIL, with HISK being strongly correlated with HIL, e.g. due to more literate individuals more likely being able to self-manage their health, should also be investigated in future research.

VI. Conclusion

This study has found a strong and statistically significant association between HISK and health insurance deductible choice in Switzerland, with higher levels of HISK associated with higher deductibles when respondents are in good health and with lower deductibles when respondents are in poor health. Given the incentives set by the high- and low-deductible plans, these results indicate more cost-conscious decision-making behaviour of high HISK individuals. The associations do not translate to the number of doctor consultations, but we cannot conclude that differences in HISK would not lead to moral hazard due to limitations in our study design for causal inference. However, we can conclude from our results that important inequalities exist in HISK in Switzerland, across different population groups, and along different dimensions of knowledge. If we believe that higher levels of HISK can improve health insurance decisions, then policy interventions should target the reduction of these inequalities in HISK to empower

individuals to make better-informed decisions about their health insurance, which is in line, for example, with the Swiss Federal Council's health policy strategy (FOPH 2019)

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This work was supported by the Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung [10001C_188851].

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Appendix

Figure A1. Distribution of HISK scores. *Source:* Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021, own calculations. The graph shows a histogram of HISK scores. For a description of the variable, see [Table 1](#).

Table A1. Estimated coefficients in the ordered logit models for deductible choice.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
HISK score	0.128 (0.023)	0.030 (0.024)	0.161 (0.038)	0.074 (0.041)
Chronic illness	-1.042 (0.169)	-0.896 (0.179)		
x HISK score	-0.106 (0.037)	-0.094 (0.039)		
Subjective health status (ref.: Very good)				
<i>Good</i>			-0.410 (0.206)	-0.276 (0.220)
x HISK score			-0.080 (0.045)	-0.089 (0.048)
<i>Fair to poor</i>			-0.938 (0.241)	-0.649 (0.265)
x HISK score			-0.225 (0.054)	-0.235 (0.059)
Age		-0.027 (0.002)		-0.031 (0.002)
Female		-0.312 (0.056)		-0.356 (0.056)
Region of residence (ref.: <i>German</i>)				
<i>French</i>		-0.054 (0.063)		0.021 (0.063)
<i>Italian</i>		-0.043 (0.095)		0.035 (0.096)
Non-Swiss		0.007 (0.097)		-0.013 (0.098)
Education (ref.: <i>Lower secondary</i>)				
<i>Upper secondary</i>		0.462 (0.113)		0.397 (0.109)
<i>Tertiary education</i>		0.905 (0.129)		0.837 (0.125)
Household income (ref.: <i>Up to 6,000</i>)				
<i>6,001–9,000</i>		0.158 (0.072)		0.159 (0.072)
<i>9,001 or higher</i>		0.361 (0.074)		0.323 (0.074)
Missing		-0.017 (0.082)		0.006 (0.082)
Risk preferences		0.351 (0.028)		0.354 (0.028)
Time preferences		0.081 (0.027)		0.081 (0.027)
<i>Threshold 1</i>	-0.530 (0.107)	-0.763 (0.219)	-0.636 (0.173)	-1.017 (0.265)
<i>Threshold 2</i>	-0.064 (0.106)	-0.248 (0.218)	-0.186 (0.173)	-0.515 (0.264)
<i>Threshold 3</i>	0.112 (0.106)	-0.049 (0.218)	-0.016 (0.173)	-0.320 (0.264)
<i>Threshold 4</i>	0.421 (0.107)	0.305 (0.218)	0.281 (0.173)	0.023 (0.264)
<i>Threshold 5</i>	0.602 (0.107)	0.512 (0.219)	0.456 (0.174)	0.226 (0.265)
Wald statistic	774.1	1297.5	608.2	1168.3
McKelvey & Zavoina's R-squared	0.148	0.276	0.120	0.262
Akaike Information Criterion	14681.2	13941.9	14877.4	14076.2
Number of observations	5,577	5,577	5,577	5,577

Source: Swiss Health Insurance Literacy Survey 2021, own calculations.

Reported numbers are estimated coefficients in four ordered logit models for the deductible amount (CHF 300, 500, 1000, 1500, 2000, or 2500) with the explanatory variables as shown in the table. For a description of the variables, see [Table 1](#). Robust standard errors are reported in parentheses.